

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Binaural Source Separation with Convolutional Neural Networks

Gerard Erruz

Supervisor: Marius Miron

Co-Supervisor: Adan Garriga

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to the fight against global warming.

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[...] they stood regarding this spectacle, this long catastrophe of foam and fury, whose preposterous roaring deafened them, frightened them, bewildered their senses of sight and hearing, so that they even imagined they heard above, below, and on all sides, cries of warning, trumpet calls, hoarse human voices.

The Magic Mountain - Thomas Mann

Abstract

This work is a study on source separation techniques for binaural music mixtures. The chosen framework uses a *Convolutional Neural Network* (CNN) to estimate time-frequency soft masks. These masks are used to extract the different sources from the original two-channel mixture signal. Its baseline single-channel architecture performed state-of-the-art results on monaural music mixtures under low-latency conditions. It has been extended to perform separation in two-channel signals, being the first two-channel CNN joint estimation architecture. This means that filters are learned for each source by taking in account both channels information. Furthermore, a specific binaural condition is included during training stage. It uses *Interaural Level Difference* (ILD) information to improve spatial images of extracted sources. Concurrently, we present a novel tool to create binaural scenes for testing purposes. Multiple binaural scenes are rendered from a music dataset of four instruments (voice, drums, bass and *others*). The CNN framework has been tested for these binaural scenes and compared with monaural and stereo results. The system showed a great amount of adaptability and good separation results in all the scenarios. These results are used to evaluate spatial information impact on separation performance.

Keywords: *Audio Source Separation; Neural Networks; Binaural; Spatial Audio*

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Conceptual background

Since the creation and development of sound recording technologies during the second half of 19th century, a whole new field emerged regarding audio processing techniques. These included storing, modification, transmission, information extraction and synthesis of audio signals. Digital audio technologies have helped on extending the limits of audio processing over the last decades. Specifically, several approaches to audio content interpretation and handling have been developed, including music transcription, automatic categorization and source separation. Thanks to the constant increasing of computing power, novel machine learning approaches have been implemented to perform audio classification and extraction tasks.

Source separation techniques are based on the segregation of a mixture in its constituent sound sources. Such a process is only possible when connected to human understanding of the nature of these sources. This means that any sound source separation task will need a previous definition or assessment on the parameters that differentiate the multiple contributions in a mixture. Spectral properties have been found useful for performing this segregation. Many approaches are based on a previous spectral definition of the sources. Other techniques, specially those based on artificial neural networks, don't need specific source information, but general guide-

lines to learn relevant information depending on each case of study. Apart from spectral information, we can foresee that multichannel signals contain new relevant parameters to improve separation tasks: panning information, channel predominance of one or multiple sources, direction of arrival, filtering differences between channels and so on.

1.2 Motivation

Apart from its inherent interest, research on sound source separation has already proved its utility in several audio processing tasks. These include automatic speech recognition (ASR) [1] [2], improving accuracy in chord recognition [3], music editing/remixing, speech intelligibility enhancement, and many other music information retrieval (MIR) tasks.

Applications of sound source separation were divided in two groups by [4]. *Audio Quality Oriented* (AQO) approaches concern mainly on retrieving the original sources signals with the maximum possible perceptive quality. In the other hand, *Significance Oriented* (SO) applications are focused to the extraction of high-level, semantic information from the separated signals. In this later case, separation results are not intended for listening purposes.

Our approach to source separation is encompassed in the AQO group, since our main goals are related to unmixing, remixing and upmixing processes. When working with musical signals we want to separate each instrument or groups of instruments, maximizing listening quality and minimizing leakage between sources. In addition to these general goals, our study focus on maintaining spatial images of each source, which has been modestly studied and represents the main contribution to state-of-the-art source separation field and spatial audio research. During the confection of the present work, an exhaustive review article was published regarding multi-microphone speech enhancement and source separation [5]. In a section dedicated to binaural multi-microphone processing, they remark that:

"The objective of a binaural noise reduction algorithm is not only to se-

lectively extract the desired speaker and to suppress interfering sources and ambient background noise, but also to preserve the auditory impression as perceived by the hearing aid user." [5]

They also mention a series of constraints when designing for hearing aids applications: low latency, fast adaptation, small number of microphones, etc.

"Designing algorithms, satisfying these constraints, and still exhibiting high noise and interference reduction together with spatial cues preservation, is still an ongoing research topic." [5]

In this thesis, we present a low latency algorithm for two-channel signals separation and discuss its results for several binaural mixtures. We focused on evaluating the impact of spatial information on separation performance. Our principal assumption is that spatial spectral cues present in binaural signals will have a positive effect in source discrimination. On the other hand, we wanted to improve spatial stability of the separated sources. This led us to implement the use of specific binaural parameters in our network architecture. We have evaluated the system in terms of learning capacity, separation quality and spatial stability of the final audio files, which links directly to the suggestions in [5]. Although our experiments have focused on music mixture signals, we think that the system can be adapted to other situations. Source separation applied to speech intelligibility enhancement is discussed in [6] for people using bilateral cochlear implants. Our study also aims to bring some light in this direction.

1.3 Objectives and structure of the report

Main objectives and structure of the present study are:

- Review and analysis of useful techniques to improve source separation in binaural signals (*Chapter 2*).

- Creation of a flexible tool to generate binaural scenes, intended for evaluation purposes. Presentation of the datasets used in our study (*Chapter 3*).
- Adaptation of a state-of-the-art source separation implementation to two-channel signals, that specifically takes advantage of binaural features to improve separation (*Chapter 4*).
- Carried experiments to assess separation performance of the system (*Chapter 4*).
- Evaluation and discussion of the separation results (*Chapter 5*).

Chapter 2

State of the Art

Three fields of study are reviewed, focusing on their relation with source separation. First, we summarize neural network conceptual and mathematical basis. Source separation background and techniques are then presented. Finally, binaural technique is explained and we review recent methods for source separation in this kind of mixtures.

2.1 Neural Networks

Artificial neural networks can be characterized as computational models with the ability to cluster, organize data and learn generalized information by performing operations based on parallel processing. Their architecture is made of layers comprising similar processing units which communicate by sending signals to each other. Connections between the units are weighted. Learning stages consist on updating the parameters of the network in order to achieve a certain condition. This parameter optimization is normally performed using a training set and its labeled ground truth to compute a loss value which has to be minimized.

2.1.1 Basic elements in a network

Each processing unit (*neurons* or *cells*) has its own

- activation state y_k , which is in turn the output of the unit;
- propagation rule, determining the effective input s_k of the unit from its external inputs;
- an activation function \mathcal{F}_k , determining the new level of activation from s_k and the current activation y_k (i.e. the update);
- an external input (*bias* or *offset*) θ_k .

Connections between units are defined by weights w_{jk} . Each particular network has a defined learning rule and takes input data from a certain external environment.

Units can be classified as *input* units if they receive data from outside the network, *output* units if they send data out of the network, and *hidden* units if they send data through the network.

Most common architectures follow *sigma* propagation rule. The total input of each neuron is then computed as follows:

$$s_k(t) = \sum_j w_{jk}(t)y_j(t) + \theta_k(t) \quad (2.1)$$

Activation function

In the general case, activation state is constantly updated by \mathcal{F}_k as

$$y_k(t+1) = \mathcal{F}_k(y_k(t), s_k(t)). \quad (2.2)$$

However, activation functions are often generalized to simpler expressions, involving only the effective input:

$$y_k = \mathcal{F}_k(s_k(t)) \quad (2.3)$$

Then, threshold functions are chosen to output contrasted data:

Logistic function:

$$\mathcal{F}_k(s_k(t)) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{s_k(t)}} \quad (2.4)$$

Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU):

$$\mathcal{F}_k(s_k(t)) = \max(0, s_k(t)) \quad (2.5)$$

Hyperbolic tangent function:

$$\mathcal{F}_k(s_k(t)) = \frac{2}{1 + e^{-2s_k(t)}} - 1 \quad (2.6)$$

2.1.2 Training of artificial neural networks

The learning process has to be performed before using the network, since it needs to adapt to the given particular problem. This involves training the network and let it change its weights according to some learning rule.

There are two distinct paradigms of learning:

- *Unsupervised learning* deals with the system's own representations of the input, without any a priori set of categories. The system creates its own classification by discovering salient features in the input set.
- *Supervised learning* consist in comparing the output of the network when processing a training set with a matching output. A loss term can be computed in order to quantize the error of the network and current learning progress.

Supervised systems are trained with a training set consisting on inputs x (X in vector notation) and outputs y (Y). The network is fed with the input set to compute

an estimated output \hat{y} , satisfying matching dimensions with y . Loss functions are computed, representing the difference between estimate and corresponding outputs. Among all possible loss functions, Euclidean distance is typically used:

$$J(w, \theta) = \|y - \hat{y}\|^2, \quad (2.7)$$

or KL divergence:

$$J(w, \theta) = \sum (y \log \frac{y}{\hat{y}} - y + \hat{y}) \quad (2.8)$$

Gradient descent and backpropagation

After defining the loss function of the system, the network has to be trained by optimizing its weights W . The usual way of doing so is to evaluate the gradient of these weights and minimize the loss iteratively. This process is commonly called *Gradient descend*. There are two ways of computing the gradient of a function:

- *Numerical gradient*. This method evaluates the function in two near points and returns the slope of the secant line through these points:

$$f'(x) \approx \frac{f(x+h) - f(x-h)}{2h} \quad (2.9)$$

where $2h$ is the step of the evaluation algorithm. The true derivative would happen in the limit case $h \rightarrow 0$. In practice it is acceptable to use a very small value of h . Computing numerical gradient is not an efficient operation, taking in account the great amount of parameters present in a neural network.

- *Analytical gradient*. A direct and very fast formula for the gradient can be derived using Calculus. However, its implementation can lead to errors and it is very common to perform a gradient check, where analytical results are compared to numerical gradient values.

Step size (or *learning rate*) becomes an important issue regarding optimization. A big step size lowers computational cost of the training process but increases the probabilities of oscillating around the minimum value of the function, leading to higher error. A lower step size could improve optimization results. A proper commitment between error and computational cost has to be evaluated for each particular system and training situation.

Backpropagation takes gradient update a step forward and proposes an analytical way of computing the gradient by using the chain rule. This allow the system to optimize relatively arbitrary loss functions efficiently, a very useful property when dealing with CNNs. A very good summary on backpropagation can be found at [7].

2.2 Audio source separation

Conceptual basis to sound source separation were introduced in [8] under the name of *Auditory Scene Analysis* (ASA). The study present the mechanisms of auditory system involved in segregating the incoming information and allocating it to individual sounds (or its mental representations). These individual contributions are called *auditory streams*. Segregation is the result of two mechanisms: sequential grouping and simultaneous grouping, which highly relate with the *Gestalt laws of grouping*.

- *Sequential grouping* connects sense data over time.
- *Simultaneous grouping* selects, from simultaneous data, those components that probably pertain to the same sound.

ASA describes human auditory perception, but was rapidly extrapolated to computer models that tried to simulate the same strategies, under the name of *Computational Auditory Scene Analysis* (CASA) [9]. Although the majority of audio source separation implementations rely on purely mathematical principles, inclusion of perceptual models such as ASA principles could bring new and improved results. Spatial information is also used for auditory scene segregation. Examples of

spatial grouping computational methods are found in [10] and [11]. Separation algorithms and performance tests proposed in the present dissertation are highly related to the ASA concept called *common location*. Our auditory system tends to group sounds which coincide spatially, and prioritizes sound streams moving continuously in space. In [12], authors study the effect of binaural filtering in auditory discrimination (spatial release effect). When dealing with binaural signals, space information can be computationally extracted from binaural cues and monaural filtering, as we'll see in Section 2.3.

Separation methods can be classified in terms of the amount of extra information they use. *Blind Source Separation* (BSS) refers to those separation tasks using no supplementary data. Strictly speaking, since all systems take some general probabilistic assumptions (e.g. *statistical independence* or *sparsity*), fully BSS implementations don't exist. *Informed Source Separation* refers to techniques where detailed prior information about the sources is needed, such as the musical score [13], text or MIDI sequence. In between these approaches, we can find methods that model sources using more complex mathematical descriptions, such as sinusoidal models or adaptive basis decompositions. This thesis will present a *supervised separation* method which assumes a prior training stage.

2.2.1 Signal model

Following the *principle of superposition*, when multiple sound waves coincide in a particular point, the resulting displacement is given by the sum of individual displacements from all concurrent waves. All this information is stored in a one-dimensional, time domain signal $x(t)$ when recording with a single microphone. Unless comparing signals from different capsules or moving a single directional microphone, spatial information is lost in the process. With this, the resulting instantaneous mixture for m channels can be represented as the linear combination of each

source's instantaneous amplitude as:

$$x_m(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N h_{mn}(t) * s_n(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^{K_{mn}} a_{mnk} s_n(t - \delta_{mnk}) \quad (2.10)$$

where x_m is the mixture signal amplitude for channel m , s_j are the signals emitted by the different sound sources (being J the total number of them), (a_{ij}, δ_{mnk}) the filters describing the path from the sources to each microphone, and h_{mn} the impulse response that models those filters. K_{mn} is the length of the impulse response (FIR filters) and the operator $*$ denotes element-wise convolution.

This convolutive mixing model applies when sources get filtered before being mixed. It happens, for example, when recording in a reverberant environment, where filters correspond to the impulse responses of the room (for each path between sources and microphones). As will be seen in Section 2.3, these impulse responses can also be replaced by *Head Related Impulse Responses* (HRIRs) when dealing with binaural mixtures.

A particular case of instantaneous mixture model is found when arriving signals are not modified by convolutive filters, and there are no differences in the time of arrival between capsules. In this *linear* model, mixture is only affected by amplitude changes between channels:

$$x_m(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N a_{mn} s_n(t) \quad (2.11)$$

These assumptions are the theoretical basis of most of the existing separation approaches. Monaural sound source separation using *Nonnegative Matrix Factorization* (NMF) is discussed in [14]. Here, each sound source is modeled as a sum of one or more spectral components learned by the algorithm. We'll discuss NFM in Section 2.2.2. Novel methods using neural networks can learn optimal and flexible hidden representations through several layers of nonlinearity. As seen in [15], deep neural networks (DNN) and recurrent neural networks (RNN) approaches can

achieve better results in separation tasks. They can be complemented with masking layers, Gaussian models and other modeling techniques in order to enforce certain constraints.

2.2.2 Audio Source Separation Techniques

Non-negative Matrix Factorization

Useful approaches to Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) are introduced in [16]. NMF techniques focus in finding non-negative factors W and H of a given non-negative matrix V such that:

$$V \approx WH \tag{2.12}$$

V is a $n \times m$ matrix where m is the number of examples in the dataset and n is the number of dimensions of the data. The interesting idea behind this approximation is that W can be regarded as containing a vector basis that is optimized for the linear approximation of the data in V . Every column of V is the result of multiplying these basis vectors by weighting values in each column of H . A good analysis is achieved when optimized basis vectors in W discover useful latent information in the original data. Optimization of both W and H is done by iterative update algorithms. New values in every iteration are found by multiplying the current value by a factor depending on the quality of the approximation in equation 2.12 (cost functions). These factors are normally Euclidean distance or other divergence values.

NMF can be applied to sound source separation by properly adapting the information contained in the matrices. A common approach is to focus on time and spectral information by defining W as the frequency contributions of each source and H as their time appearances [17]. Temporal evolution for local description of each source is introduced in [18]. Still, the main drawback of NMF approaches remains on their static nature, since no global time evolution can be inferred. Further research has been carried on NMF applications for source separation, specifically

for Singing Voice Separation (SVS). In [19], the authors propose a previous step for voiced/unvoiced classification of the signal content using audio descriptors such as *MFCC*, *PLP* and *LPC*. This allows to group all vocal fragments to model better time-spectral descriptions. In [20], an extended NMF model is proposed for multichannel audio data, exploring the redundancy of data between channels and the modeling of sources by superimposed Gaussian components.

Deep Neural Networks

Deep Neural Networks (DNN) have recently caught attention due to their flexibility and improving results on source separation tasks. In [21], an informed main instrument extraction system is proposed. The network is built of *Rectified Linear Units* (ReLU) with an input consisting on the *Short Time Fourier Transform* (STFT) of frames of the desired mixture signal. Main and accompanying instruments are known, so authors built a dataset of solo performances of each instrument to train the network.

Recently, other kind of networks have been proposed, such as *Convolutional Neural Networks* (CNNs) in [22]. This was the first approach to Music Separation involving CNNs, while other systems have also applied this kind of networks to automatic speech recognition [23]. CNNs focus on local spatial correlation among input neurons to learn localized features. This is exploited for learning source properties in the spectrogram of the mixture. These properties are then used to estimate time-frequency soft masks for each source. Masks can be directly applied to the original mixture to output estimates of the sources. These estimates are then added to the original phase of the mixture to obtain the separated audio signals. A more detailed explanation of this system's architecture will be discussed in Chapter 4. Multichannel approaches have been also studied and implemented. The method proposed in [24] extends the use of Wiener filters to handle spectral information in multichannel signals.

2.2.3 Evaluation

Assessing performance on audio source separation results is not a trivial issue. We are dealing here with subjective perception of sources and noise, with different context situations, and also with different use cases. A simple evaluation metric would be to compute the l^2 normalized difference between the estimated source \hat{s}_j and the target source s_j :

$$D = \min_{\epsilon=\pm 1} \left\| \frac{\hat{s}_j}{\|\hat{s}_j\|} - \epsilon \frac{s_j}{\|s_j\|} \right\|^2 \quad (2.13)$$

which satisfies $0 < D < 2$. The difference equals to zero if and only if $\hat{s}_j = s_j$ and is limited to a maximum of 2 even in the worst case scenario, thanks to normalization. This measure can give us relevant information about the separation performance, but lacks specificity on pointing out different contributions to the observed deviation. In [25], authors propose a series of measures to objectify blind audio source separation performance, taking in account different applications for the separated sources. They consider a mixture as a linear sum of its sources $(s_j)_{j \in J}$ and background noise n_i . First of all, a decomposition of the estimated source is assumed:

$$\hat{s}_j = s_{target} + e_{interf} + e_{noise} + e_{artif} \quad (2.14)$$

Here, the different contributions are:

- s_{target} , a modified version of the original source signal containing allowed distortions \mathcal{F} . So it can be presented as $s_{target} = f(s_j), f \in \mathcal{F}$;
- e_{interf} holds for distortion coming from other sources in the original mixture (leakage);
- e_{noise} is the remaining distortion from the original noise signal of the mixture;
- e_{artif} refers to artifacts not coming from signal present in the original mixture. They mostly appear due to self-generated distortion from the algorithm.

These parameters are computed by projecting estimate signal into different vectorial subspaces containing original sources and noise signals. Orthogonal projection is introduced in the form of the operator $\Pi\{y_i, \dots, y_k\}$. This operator is a $T \times T$ matrix (T is the dimension of each element its subspace) that performs orthogonal projection into the $\{y_i, \dots, y_k\}$ subspace. With this, we can define

$$P_{s_j} := \Pi\{s_j\}, \quad (2.15)$$

$$P_s := \Pi\{(s_{j'})_{1 \leq j' \leq n}\}, \quad (2.16)$$

$$P_{s,n} := \Pi\{(s_{j'})_{1 \leq j' \leq n}, (n_i)_{1 \leq i \leq m}\} \quad (2.17)$$

to obtain the desired separate contributions:

$$s_{target} = P_{s_j} \hat{s}_j, \quad (2.18)$$

$$e_{interf} = P_s \hat{s}_j - P_{s_j} \hat{s}_j, \quad (2.19)$$

$$e_{noise} = P_{s,n} \hat{s}_j - P_s \hat{s}_j, \quad (2.20)$$

$$e_{artif} = \hat{s}_j - P_{s,n} \hat{s}_j. \quad (2.21)$$

These contributions can be quantified using energy ratios in dB. Authors propose to compute four different quantities. They define the *Source to Distortion Ratio*

$$SDR := 10 \log_{10} \frac{\|s_{target}\|^2}{\|e_{interf} + e_{noise} + e_{artif}\|^2}, \quad (2.22)$$

the *Source to Interferences Ratio*

$$SIR := 10 \log_{10} \frac{\|s_{target}\|^2}{\|e_{interf}\|^2}, \quad (2.23)$$

the *Sources to Noise Ratio*

$$SNR := 10 \log_{10} \frac{\|s_{target} + e_{interf}\|^2}{\|e_{noise}\|^2}, \quad (2.24)$$

and the *Sources to Artifacts Ratio*

$$SAR := 10 \log_{10} \frac{\|s_{target} + e_{interf} + e_{noise}\|^2}{\|e_{artif}\|^2}. \quad (2.25)$$

Further extensions of this metrics are presented in [26]. This publication introduces the *Image to Spatial distortion Ratio* for evaluating separation in stereo mixes:

$$ISR_j := 10 \log_{10} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^I (s_{ij}^{img})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^I (e_{ij}^{spat})^2}. \quad (2.26)$$

Here, e_{ij}^{spat} refers to the error in preserving the image (filtering) of source j as found in its original channel i . s_{ij}^{img} is the original signal of source i in channel j . I is the total number of channels.

These metrics relate mostly to practical purposes on production and MIR tasks. For example, SIR can be a good indicator when we are planning to use the separated tracks in a new context. If an instrument track is removed, interferences from it could be annoying in the new mix. SAR, in the other hand, gives information of the direct degradation of the signal by the sole fact of using the separation algorithm.

2.3 Binaural

2.3.1 Binaural basics

The binaural technique is based on our perceptual mechanisms for locating sound sources in space. As stated by Rayleigh in [27], our brain relies mainly on two cues to determine the direction of arrival of a certain sound:

- *Interaural Level Difference*. Each ear receives the signal with different intensities due to shadowing by our head and torso. This is only relevant for high frequencies unless the source is located very close to one ear.
- *Interaural Time Difference*. Time of arrival is different for each ear and phase of the signal is then relevant to locate sources (mainly for low frequencies).

Yet, some directions share the exact same cues and set the so-called cones of confusion [28] (Figure 1). This kind of situation is solved by the effect of filtering in the interaction of sound waves and the auditory system (pinna and ear canal) or by small movements of the head.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the cone of confusion. Adapted from [29]. ©2012 Giulio Cengarle.

In terms of theoretical recreation of all these effects, audio signal processing techniques use specific filters, called *Head Related Impulse Responses* (HRIRs). They encode spatial information in usual stereo files (Figure 2). These filters contain the desired ITD/ILD and monaural cues. Resulting signals are normally reproduced via headphones, since it is the easiest way of sending each respective channel to each ear avoiding cross-talking drawbacks. Still, binaural reproduction using loudspeakers has been also developed under the name of *transaural* reproduction, using specific filters to perform cross-talk cancellation [30].

2.3.2 Binaural in Source Separation

There are already some studies that exploit binaural properties to improve source separation results. One of the examples of binaural feature extraction for DNN

Figure 2: HRIR signals for each ear. Time difference between their first peaks is called ITD, and amplitude difference of both peaks is called ILD. Monaural cues are derived from the properties of each signal.

training is presented in [31]. Speech signal extraction is analyzed in the case of reverberant environments and concurrent noise. For this, a binary classifier is proposed: each frame is classified whether having predominant voice contribution or not. The chosen framework is a DNN with both binaural and monaural features as inputs of the system. Extracted binaural cues are the usual ITD and ILD between each ear signal. As monaural feature, *Gammatone Frequency Cepstral Coefficients* are extracted from one of the channels. This feature enhances performance specifically when speech and noise contributions are close spatially. Feature extraction is performed as follows:

- *Interaural Time Difference*: ITD is estimated as the lag corresponding to the maximum in the cross-correlation function:

$$ITD(c, m) = \arg_{\tau} \max CCF(c, m, \tau) \quad (2.27)$$

where CCF is the normalized cross-correlation function between the two ear signals, c denotes a filter channel, m is the current frame and τ is the time lag.

- *Interaural Level Difference*: ILD corresponds to the energy ration between the

channels, in dB:

$$ILD(c, m) = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \frac{\sum_k x_{cm,l}^2(k)}{\sum_k x_{cm,r}^2(k)} \quad (2.28)$$

where variable definitions hold from previous ITD example and l, r refer to left and right channels respectively.

Their DNN architecture consists on an input layer (fed with feature vector of each T-F unit pair), 2 hidden layers for training and one-neuron output layer with a binary label indicating speech dominance. Training is performed by a *Mini-batch Gradient Descent* algorithm.

Other studies extract binaural cues information in the time-frequency domain by computing the Short-Term Fourier transform (STFT) of the signal, as seen in [32] and [33]. First, each channel spectrogram is computed as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} s_{ft}^{(L)} &= h_f^{(L)}(\mathbf{x}) s_{ft}^{(S)} \\ s_{ft}^{(R)} &= h_f^{(R)}(\mathbf{x}) s_{ft}^{(S)} \end{aligned} \right\}, \quad (2.29)$$

where $(s_{ft}^{(S)})_{f,t=1}^{F,T}$ is the complex-valued spectrogram emitted by the source, and $(s_{ft}^{(L)})_{f,t=1}^{F,T}$, $(s_{ft}^{(R)})_{f,t=1}^{F,T}$ the perceived left and right spectrograms respectively. $\mathbf{h}^{(L)}$ and $\mathbf{h}^{(R)}$ denote the left and right non-linear HRTFs.

The *interaural transfer function* (ITF) is then defined as

$$I_f(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\mathbf{h}^{(R)}}{\mathbf{h}^{(L)}} \quad (2.30)$$

and the *interaural spectrogram* is defined as

$$\hat{I}_{ft} = \frac{s_{ft}^{(R)}}{s_{ft}^{(L)}} \quad (2.31)$$

so that $\hat{I}_{ft} = I_f(\mathbf{x})$. This formulation ensures that \hat{I}_{ft} doesn't depend on the emitted spectrogram, but only on the emitting source position \mathbf{x} . This equality holds only when $s_{ft}^{(S)} \neq 0$, this is, when the source is emitting in that frequency bin. As we will be dealing with sparse spectrograms, a binary variable is introduced to overcome this condition and characterize missing values:

$$\chi_{ft} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if the value is missing} \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.32)$$

As an example, a sound source emitting white noise from position \mathbf{x} holds $\chi_{ft} = 1$ for all (f, t) because it is constantly emitting at all frequencies.

From 2.31, ILD spectrogram α and IPD spectrogram ϕ are defined as the log-amplitude and phase of \hat{I}_{ft} :

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_{ft} = 20 \log \|\hat{I}_{ft}\| \in \mathbb{R} \\ \phi_{ft} = \exp(j \arg(\hat{I}_{ft})) \in \mathbb{C} \end{cases} \quad (2.33)$$

Their temporal means (*mean interaural vectors*) can be defined as $\bar{\alpha} \in \mathbb{R}^F$ and $\bar{\phi} \in \mathbb{R}^{2F}$ for each position. Duplex theory proposed by Rayleigh [34] and further studied in [35], states that ITDs are used to locate low frequencies (below 2kHz), while ILDs are mostly used in high frequency sounds (above 2 kHz). Authors in [33] suggest to define distinct vectors for mean *low*-ILD, *high*-ILD, *low*-ITD and *high*-ITD. Here, *low* refers to frequencies between 300 and 2000 Hz, and *high* refers to frequencies above 2 kHz. Frequencies between 0 and 300 Hz don't contain significant information due to a high amount of noise in this range.

Effect of binaural cues on *Blind Source Separation* (BSS) results is also tested in [36]. Their approach is intended for improving speech recognition in bilateral cochlear implant patients, taking advantage of the position of the implants, one for each ear. A BSS algorithm is implemented using a single processor dealing with the two channels. Proposed BSS algorithm is formulated using a convolutive approach.

ITD information is learned as filter delays applied to the original signal, while ILDs are expressed as variations in the filters coefficients. After training the system, they performed two experiments with bilateral cochlear implant patients (and also a non-implanted group). Results show that spatial information is used mostly in non-reverberant environments, since reverberation cues tend to blur temporal and spectral cues, and mask other important properties used for sound localization and speech recognition.

More general approaches have been discussed recently, involving covariance matrices to encode spatial information. A multiple-DNNs system is introduced in [24] and extended in [37]. Here, a first DNN predicts source spectrograms by computing time-frequency masks for each source. Then, an Expectation-Maximization iterative algorithm is used to estimate parameters and compute a multichannel Wiener filter that contains spectral and also spatial information. This information is held in the spatial covariance matrix (R) and the *Power Spectral Density* from estimated spectrograms. This is also explained and extended in [38], [39] and [40]. Different computations of R are presented, being *Rank-1 Convolutional Model* a good candidate for handling binaural spatial information using known HRTFs. This could open a new field of study on using known locations of the sources to enhance separation performance (*location-informed*).

Chapter 3

Datasets

This chapter contains all the information related to the datasets we used for our experiments. A novel tool is presented to create customized binaural scenes for testing purposes. Then, we explain the binaural datasets we created for the present study.

3.1 Binaural scene generation tool

For training and testing the proposed architecture (discussed in Section 4.1), we created a code [41] to generate controlled binaural scenes. It aims to be a flexible way of creating multiple binaural versions of existing datasets in order to test how separation algorithms perform in different conditions. Taking this flexibility approach in account, the code uses the *Binaural Simulator* provided by *Two!Ears Auditory Model* framework [42]. This integration permits the user to choose individual angular positions for each source in the horizontal plane. Positions can change for every song in the dataset. User can also import any set of *Head Related Transfer Functions* (HRTFs) for the generation of the binaural signals. These transfer functions include monaural and interaural filtering, and also the acoustic response of the room. The default set of HRTFs were measured with a *KEMAR* dummy head in the anechoic chamber of the *TU Berlin* [43] with 1 meter distance between source and listener. Distance can also be modified, although Otani et al. [44] showed that distance has

few influence in HRTFs shape.

Under the scope of this thesis, we worked with the *Demixing Secrets Dataset 100* (DSD100). The original DSD100 was introduced in *MUS 2016* campaign [45] and consists of 100 professionally mixed songs of different styles. Mixture and separate tracks are provided for each song. Included instruments are classified as: vocals, drums, bass and *other*. The set is divided equally between *Test* and *Development* subsets, the latter intended for supervised training purposes. All tracks are stored as stereo *WAV* files with sample rate of $44.1kHz$.

New datasets can be then generated, following the same structure as the original DSD100: the final binaural mixture is saved for both subsets (*Test* and *Development*), while individual positioned tracks are also saved. Position of the individual source signal and its location in the binaural mixture are the same.

3.2 Binaural scenes

A series of binaural scenes have been generated to test the two-channel algorithm.

3.2.1 Binaural Cross

All the songs in this dataset are encoded using the same angular positions for each of the sources. The four sources are located in cross formation as seen in Figure 3. Angular values for each source are collected in Table 1. This dataset is intended to test how separation improves when the source is present predominantly in one of the channels (here, *vocals* and *other*), and how the algorithm deals with front/back locations, where the source signal is equally distributed in both channels (*drums* and *bass*).

Figure 3: Schematic representation of source location setup for Binaural Cross dataset.

Table 1: Source angular positions for Binaural Cross dataset.

Source	Angular position (in degrees)
Voice	90 ± 1
Drums	0 ± 1
Bass	180 ± 1
Other	270 ± 1

3.2.2 Binaural Xeix

Here, all the songs in the dataset are encoded using the same angular positions for each of the sources. The four sources are located in *xeix* (X) formation as seen in Figure 4. Angular values for each source are collected in Table 2. This dataset is intended to test how separation performs when two sources are equally present in each channel in terms of intensity, but having different binaural filtering.

Figure 4: Schematic representation of source location setup for Binaural Xeix dataset.

Table 2: Source angular positions for Binaural Xeix dataset.

Source	Angular position (in degrees)
Voice	45 ± 1
Drums	315 ± 1
Bass	135 ± 1
Other	225 ± 1

3.2.3 Binaural Random

In this binaural dataset, sources are located in random positions for each song. This setup is intended to prevent the network from learning specific position filtering (HRTFs) and focus on source properties as in monaural case.

3.2.4 Binaural Static Random

Here, all the songs in the dataset are encoded using the same angular positions for each of the sources, but random positions have been chosen. As we can see in Figure 5, this dataset recreates a more natural situation, where sources are distributed in the front half circle of the listener and some of them are located very close to each other. Angular values are collected in Table 3.

Table 3: Source angular positions for Binaural Static Random dataset.

Source	Angular position (in degrees)
Voice	326 ± 1
Drums	293 ± 1
Bass	46 ± 1
Other	329 ± 1

Figure 5: Schematic representation of source location setup for Binaural Static Random dataset.

Chapter 4

Methodology

In this chapter, we explain the proposed method and its implementation, the chosen parameters for the network, and the conducted experiments to test separation performance. We also explain the materials used for the processing and the dismissed alternative configurations.

4.1 System architecture

4.1.1 Baseline architecture

This thesis contributions are based on *DeepConvSep* system, a *Convolutional Neural Network* (CNN) implementation documented in [22]. It was submitted to source separation evaluation campaigns such as *Music Information Retrieval Evaluation eXchange 2016* (MIREX 2016) and performed state-of-the-art results in low-latency conditions.

Basic concepts regarding this neural network architecture are:

- *Convolutional layer*. This kind of layer contains a set of filters with defined widths and heights. They have the same depth as the input volume. The values of the filters are learned during the training process. Each filter behave as a convolutional unit: it slides across the input's width and height and

performs dot product with the comprised volume. Results of these operations are stored in a new output matrix. It acts as an activation map, where a high value indicates that a particular pattern has been detected.

- *Bias layer.* This layer adds an extra parameter to each value of the input volume: a bias constant value that is updated during the training stage.
- *Fully Connected Layer.* Each neuron in this layer is connected to each output of the previous layer. These neurons perform a fixed mathematical operation on the input value, depending on the non-linear function they hold (e.g. *ReLU*, *Sigmoid*)
- *Autoencoder.* This kind of neural network is meant to deal with unlabeled training examples by ensuring equal dimensions on input and output volumes. Backpropagation is performed by comparing the output of the network with a target ground-truth volume.
- *Soft mask.* This kind of mask is also called *proportional mask*, since it is a normalization of the contribution of each source for each spectral bin in the original mixture signal.

In our particular case, the input of the network consists of a spectrogram of fixed dimensions:

$$\text{Input volume dimensions}_{\text{monaural}} = (\text{batch size, time context, spectral resolution}) \quad (4.1)$$

Spectrograms are computed by taking 30 second chunks from each signal (mixtures and individual sources) as seen in Figure 6. As *DeepConvSep* implementation deals with monaural signals, any stereo mixture will be downmixed to mono by adding the two stereo channels.

This framework is a *convolutional autoencoder* that comprises two main stages and a *Fully Connected Layer*. The input of the network is the spectrogram matrix of the

Figure 6: Schematic representation of the feature extraction (spectrograms) to input into *DeepConvSep* neural network [22].

mixture. After going through the network, the output volumes store four copies with the same dimensions as the original input. Each copy will be compared to a different ground-truth source spectrogram during training phase. The specific architecture of this network (Figure 7) contains the following blocks:

1. *Convolution stage*: it consists of two convolution layers. As its input is the mixture spectrogram, convolution filters learn timbre features for each source by updating weight values during the training process. The second convolutional layer learns temporal information from the timbre features extracted before.
2. *Fully Connected Layer*: this *ReLU* layer is an information bottleneck to perform dimensional reduction. It avoids overfitting for guarantying a robust representation of the data.
3. *Deconvolution network*: reduced data is up-sampled by different deconvolution layers that perform inverse operations of the convolutional stage. It outputs the four estimate spectrograms.

Figure 7: Schematic representation of the monaural *DeepConvSep* network architecture [22].

A time-frequency mask $m_n(f)$ is computed from those estimates as:

$$m_n(f) = \frac{\|\hat{y}_n(f)\|}{\sum_{n=1}^N \|\hat{y}_n(f)\|} \quad (4.2)$$

being $\hat{y}_n(f)$ the output of the network for source n and N is the total number of sources. These masks are applied to the original input mixture signal spectrogram $x(f)$ to obtain the final estimate of each source:

$$\tilde{y}_n(f) = m_n(f)x(f) \quad (4.3)$$

The learning steps of the training stage are based on *Stochastic Gradient Descent* parameter optimization, using *AdaDelta* algorithm [46], which is based on the min-

imization of the squared error between the estimate and the original source y_n as

$$L_{\text{sq}} = \sum_{i=1}^N \|\tilde{y}_n - y_n\|^2 \quad (4.4)$$

Loss parameter is then computed as the sum of squared errors from *vocals*, *drums* and *bass* signals:

$$\text{loss} = L_{\text{sq,vocals}} + L_{\text{sq,drums}} + L_{\text{sq,bass}} \quad (4.5)$$

4.1.2 Two-channel extension

A new implementation has been adapted to handle two-channel signals by duplicating aforementioned steps and computing estimates for each source in each channel. This is the first two-channel joint estimation architecture, since filters are computed jointly for each source taking in account information in both channels.

First of all, feature extraction algorithm have been modified to save spectrogram information for each channel, removing the monaural downmix step (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Schematic representation of the feature extraction (spectrograms) to input into the two-channel architecture.

Following these changes, the new network architecture has to handle an input volume with an extra dimension (handling the number of channels):

$$\text{Input volume dimensions}_{\text{two-channel}} = (\text{batch size, number of channels,} \quad (4.6) \\ \text{time context, spectral resolution})$$

The network computes estimates for each channel following the same steps as in the monaural implementation (Figure 9). The output volume contains eight estimate spectrograms, one for each source in each channel.

Figure 9: Schematic representation of the extended two-channel architecture.

A particular soft mask step is computed for each channel l and source n :

$$m_{ln}(f) = \frac{\|\hat{y}_{ln}(f)\|}{\sum_{n=1}^N \|\hat{y}_{ln}(f)\|} \quad (4.7)$$

from which final estimates are obtained:

$$\tilde{y}_{ln}(f) = m_{ln}(f)x_i(f) \quad (4.8)$$

Loss is computed as the addition of each channel loss term as in monaural case:

$$\begin{aligned} loss_{\text{two-channel}} = & (L_{\text{sq,vocals,left}} + L_{\text{sq,drums,left}} + L_{\text{sq,bass,left}}) + \\ & (L_{\text{sq,vocals,right}} + L_{\text{sq,drums,right}} + L_{\text{sq,bass,right}}) \end{aligned} \quad (4.9)$$

4.1.3 Interaural spectrogram loss

A new contribution on spatial learning has been studied and implemented, using *interaural spectrograms* to hold spatial information of each source position. *Interaural spectrograms* are computed as proposed in [33] (already summarized in Section 2.3.2), and reduced to magnitude ILD spectrograms. Since these spectrograms hold interaural information, they can be a good feature from which the network learns spatial information. This information is used as a condition to keep the original spatial image of each source. This idea is implemented and tested by including a new loss contribution (*ILD loss*).

ILD loss is defined as the comparison between the ILD *mean interaural vector* ($\bar{\alpha}$) of each source estimate and that of each ground-truth source signal. These vectors are computed following equations 2.31 and 2.33 and taking the temporal mean of the ILD spectrogram. The new loss contribution is updated by computing the squared error:

$$L_{\text{ILD}} = \sum_{i=1}^N \|\bar{\alpha}'_n - \bar{\alpha}_n\|^2, \quad (4.10)$$

where $\bar{\alpha}'_n$ comes from estimated source signals and $\bar{\alpha}_n$ is computed from ground-truth source signals.

Two-stage training

ILD loss contribution is implemented as a final training stage. Spatial information is better extracted when estimated sources have less leakage from other sources. That's why the first training stage uses the original loss from equation 4.9. A second training stage finally incorporates spatial information in the loss function, following:

$$loss_{\text{ILD}} = loss_{\text{two-channel}} + A \cdot L_{\text{ILD}} \quad (4.11)$$

being A an arbitrary scalar used to balance loss contributions. In our case, A is empirically set to $\frac{1}{1000}$ in order to have approximately the same order in both contributions.

4.2 Computational framework and materials

In order to implement the system explained below, we've used the Python library *Lasagne* [47], which is meant for building and training neural networks in *Theano* [48]. These libraries permit to organize a proper data flow used in CNN architecture. Training stages has been performed by a computer with a GeForce GTX TITAN X GPU, Intel Core i7-5820K 3.3GHz 6-Core Processor, and X99 gaming 5 x99 ATX DDR44 motherboard.

4.3 Dismissed alternative configurations

Here, we collect a list of tested alternative network configurations, which showed no improvements for the present research:

- Non-joint network architecture with separate filters for each channel.
- Computing final separate signals using separate ground-truth phase instead of original mixture phase.
- Applying *high*-ILD condition to compute ILD spectrogram mean values instead of taking the whole frequency range (discussed in section 2.3.2).

4.4 Evaluation setup

Training stage is based on the comparison of estimate spectrogram (obtained from that of the original mixture) and ground-truth separate source spectrogram. This feature extraction is performed by dividing each song (mixture and separate sources) in 30 second chunks and computing their STFT with the following parameters: a frame size of 1024 samples, a hop size of 512 samples (50% overlap) and a *Hanning* window applied to each frame. Sample rate is maintained (at $44100Hz$ for DSD100 case). These spectrograms are fed to the network in form of batches. These batches contain a certain number (batch size) of frames extracted from the input spectrogram, its size depending on the chosen time context and with a certain time overlap. An epoch finishes when every sample in the set have gone through the network. This is meant to optimize and maximize learning performance from spectrogram data. Based on network optimization by Pritish (2016) [22], we chose the parameters contained in Table 4:

Table 4: Training parameters chosen for the proposed CNN architecture.

Parameter	Value
Batch size	32 frames
Time context	30 samples
Time overlap	25 samples (83.3%)
First convolutional layer shape	$(f_1 = 513, t_1 = 1)$ samples
Second convolutional layer shape	$(f_2 = 1, t_2 = 15)$ samples
First convolutional layer stride	(1, 1) samples
Second convolutional layer stride	(1, 1) samples
Number of filters in each convolutional layer	50 filters
Bottleneck	256 units
Number of epochs (stage 1)	30 epochs
Number of epochs (stage 2)	15 epochs

Once separation results are obtained, these are evaluated using metrics proposed by [26], already discussed in Section 2.2.3. There are *Source to Distortion Ratio* (SDR), *Source to Interferences Ratio* (SIR), *Sources to Artifacts Ratio* (SAR) and *Image to Spatial distortion Ratio* (ISR). They are averaged over the overlapping 30 second frames of each song in the dataset.

4.5 Experiments

We carried out two different experiments:

4.5.1 Experiment 1: Separation performance

We trained a model for each dataset, using only the *Dev* subset. Training parameters are described in Table 4. After this, source separation was performed for both *Dev* and *Test* subsets.

4.5.2 Experiment 2: Comparison between ILD model and non-ILD model

We took *BDS100 Static Random* and *BDS100 Xeix* datasets. We trained two models for each dataset (only *Dev* subsets): a model containing ILD condition, and another one computed without the second training stage. All the other parameters were maintained as in Table 4. After this, source separation is performed for both *Dev* and *Test* subsets.

Chapter 5

Results and discussion

This chapter contains the results from the experiments described in Section 4.5 and the subsequent discussion. The processed datasets are: the original DSD100 stereo mixtures, a monaural version of it (generated by doubling a previously downmixed version), and a series of binaural scenes generated with the tool discussed in Section 3.1. Evaluation metrics have been discussed in Section 2.2.3.

5.1 Tables and graphics

5.1.1 Experiment 1

Figures 10, 11 and 12 show the separation results for Experiment 1. Values are collected in tables 5, 6 and 7, respectively.

Figure 10: Evaluation metrics (SDR, ISR, SIR and SAR) comparison for each dataset in experiment 1. Error bars indicate the standard error of the measurement.

Table 5: Values of the evaluation metrics (SDR, ISR, SIR and SAR) for each dataset in experiment 1. Error values indicate the standard error of the measurement.

	SDR (dB)	ISR (dB)	SIR (dB)	SAR (dB)
BDS100 Cross	3.40 ± 0.04	4.35 ± 0.05	7.12 ± 0.07	9.03 ± 0.06
BDS100 Random	2.28 ± 0.03	3.38 ± 0.04	4.90 ± 0.08	6.22 ± 0.07
BDS100 Static Random	2.74 ± 0.03	3.85 ± 0.04	6.55 ± 0.07	6.14 ± 0.06
BDS100 Xeix	3.50 ± 0.04	4.13 ± 0.04	7.84 ± 0.08	9.16 ± 0.05
DSD100	3.56 ± 0.04	7.05 ± 0.04	4.71 ± 0.07	7.03 ± 0.04
MDS100 Random	3.46 ± 0.04	6.93 ± 0.04	4.49 ± 0.08	6.88 ± 0.04

Figure 11: SDR comparison for each source in each dataset in experiment 1. Error bars indicate the standard error of the measurement.

Table 6: SDR values for each source in each dataset in experiment 1. Error values indicate the standard error of the measurement.

	SDR (dB)			
	Bass	Drums	Other	Vocals
BDS100 Cross	1.52 ± 0.02	1.45 ± 0.04	4.13 ± 0.06	6.53 ± 0.07
BDS100 Random	2.03 ± 0.03	1.43 ± 0.05	2.79 ± 0.07	2.85 ± 0.08
BDS100 Static Random	2.55 ± 0.05	1.62 ± 0.03	2.74 ± 0.04	4.08 ± 0.07
BDS100 Xeix	1.43 ± 0.02	3.87 ± 0.06	1.97 ± 0.03	6.75 ± 0.08
DSD100	3.22 ± 0.07	4.33 ± 0.08	2.71 ± 0.06	3.98 ± 0.07
MDSD100 Random	3.23 ± 0.07	4.38 ± 0.09	2.28 ± 0.06	3.96 ± 0.07

Figure 12: Comparison of the SDR from *Development* and *Test* subsets for each dataset in experiment 1. Error bars indicate the standard error of the measurement.

Table 7: SDR values from *Development* and *Test* subsets for each dataset in experiment 1. Error values indicate the standard error of the measurement.

	SDR (dB)	
	Dev	Test
BSD100 Cross	3.42 ± 0.06	3.38 ± 0.06
BSD100 Random	2.86 ± 0.04	1.64 ± 0.04
BSD100 Static Random	3.00 ± 0.04	2.46 ± 0.04
BSD100 Xeix	3.53 ± 0.06	3.45 ± 0.06
DSD100	4.24 ± 0.05	2.81 ± 0.05
MDSD100 Random	4.05 ± 0.05	2.83 ± 0.05

5.1.2 Experiment 2

Figure 13 shows the separation results for Experiment 2. Values are collected in Table 8.

Figure 13: Evaluation metrics (SDR, SIR and SAR) comparison between datasets in experiment 2. Error bars indicate the standard error of the measurement.

Table 8: Evaluation metrics (SDR, ISR, SIR and SAR) values for each dataset in experiment 2. Error values indicate the standard error of the measurement.

	SDR (dB)	ISR (dB)	SIR (dB)	SAR (dB)
BDS100 Static Random	2.74 ± 0.03	3.85 ± 0.04	6.69 ± 0.07	6.21 ± 0.06
BDS100 Static Random (no ILD)	2.89 ± 0.03	4.12 ± 0.04	7.12 ± 0.07	6.05 ± 0.06
BDS100 Xeix	3.50 ± 0.04	4.13 ± 0.05	8.87 ± 0.09	9.20 ± 0.05
BDS100 Xeix (no ILD)	3.84 ± 0.04	4.56 ± 0.05	9.92 ± 0.09	9.40 ± 0.06

5.2 Discussion

5.2.1 Predominance effect

Binaural music mixtures present a differential factor when compared to stereo or monaural signals: sources have high possibilities to be predominantly panned to one of the channels. This fact has two main effects in our system’s separation performance. When dealing with binaural mixtures,

- The system is able to learn individual properties from cleaner mixtures.
- Separation is less complex, since there is less leakage between sources in the target mixture. There is little chance of finding all the sources in a single channel.

These two conditions are not usually found in stereo mixtures and are obviously impossible in monaural signals. Stereo music mixtures contain panning differences between instruments (voice and drums are usually in the middle, while bass and *other* are more often on the side), but they have had little effect on our separation results.

Predominance effect becomes clear in *SIR* results in Figure 10. Leakage between sources is minimized when the system has the opportunity to learn each instrument properties from cleaner mixtures. All the binaural scenes (except the case of *BDS100 Random*, discussed below) show better results than stereo and monaural datasets.

On the other hand, *SDR* results of *other* instrument show the importance of predominance in separation stage. We have to remember that *other* is not included in the loss contribution, so it is not taken in account in the learning stage. Its specially good results in *BDS100 Cross* dataset show that being predominant in a channel enhances separation performance.

SAR results shows that final signals are less prone to artifacts when they have predominant sources. This can be related to the final level of the signals (lower when mixing a higher number of sources into the same channel) and its gain relation to artifacts signal level.

5.2.2 Position learning

Results show several evidences of position learning by the system. *SIR* results from Figure 10 show a noticeable difference between *BDS100 Random* dataset and all the other binaural datasets. Position learning can be achieved by learning the predominance of a source in a certain channel and also by learning the specific binaural filtering of the source position. The random nature of *BDS100 Random* dataset doesn't allow the system to learn position information. This is also highlighted in Figure 12, that evidences a performance descent of this dataset when dealing with new mixtures (*Test* subset), while static binaural datasets show more stable results.

5.2.3 Spatial image stability and ILD condition

ILD condition effects are clear in terms of numerical results: our metrics show a general loss of quality due to this extra learning stage. Given the way it has been implemented within the network, this condition imposes a trade-off between maintaining spectral properties and keeping ILD untouched. From numerical results, we can infer that ILD condition is adding dissimilarities between estimated source and ground-truth source signals.

However, informal listening tests showed varied perceptive results when comparing separation performed with an ILD model vs. separation using a model exempt from this condition. ILD condition seems to improve spatial stability when sources have less spectral leakage between them. For example, separated *vocals* from *BDS100 Xeix* dataset show a clear improvement in spatial stability. In this dataset, *vocals* share predominance with *bass* in their main channel. There is low spectral leakage between these two sources and ILD condition can be applied without losing a great amount of spectral quality in the final separated signals.

On the other hand, this is not happening in *BDS100 Static Random* dataset. In this case, *vocals* are sharing predominance with *drums* and *others* and ILD condition doesn't bring positive perceptive results. This is due to another effect: when losing spectral content quality in the learning stage, more amplitude fluctuations appear in the final separated signals. This fluctuations, by being independent of the channel, have a highly negative effect in spatial image stability.

We have to notice that spatial image and externalization is fairly maintained without ILD condition, and improvements enter the domain of finesse. However, they can play an important role in certain applications, e.i. real-time separation for bilateral cochlear implants.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

6.1 Conclusions

The proposed system achieved good separation results for all tested cases: monaural, stereo, and the binaural scenes. This is the first joint estimation CNN architecture, and this work proves the high adaptability of the system.

Performance in binaural signals showed variable but promising separation results in music mixtures. This is empowering to further research in this direction, while extending the cases of study to other audio separation tasks. Source separation on binaural signals leads directly to hearing aids applications, such as speech enhancing for bilateral cochlear implants.

The concept of spatial stability, both for stereo and binaural signals, has been explored in an embryonic stage and requires further research. Our architecture seems to maintain spatial spectral information for itself, with or without ILD condition. But other kind of separation systems could need stronger stability conditions.

6.2 Contributions

This work has two slopes. The first one is focused on the study and discussion of the effect of spatial information in binaural source separation. This is held in chapters 2

and 5. The second one has involved the development of two novel implementations: a binaural scene generation tool, to create controlled binaural datasets (Chapter 3), and a two-channel source separation tool that can take advantage of binaural information to improve spatial stability (Chapter 4).

These two systems are publicly available in the following repositories:

Binaural_DSD100

https://github.com/gerruz/binaural_DSD100

Two-channel CNN separation system

This system has been included in *DeepConvSep* repository:

<https://github.com/MTG/DeepConvSep> (inside the *examples* folder).

With this, we aim to motivate community contribution and feedback. Publicly releasing the computational tools used in this dissertation is also a way of ensuring the reproducibility of its results.

6.3 Further work

This study can be seen as a preliminary research that opens new questions and directions in the field of spatial information retrieval and source separation for spatial audio. Test on binaural scenes need to be extended by defining a specific objective evaluation framework. Due to the subjective nature of binaural perception, proper listening tests have to be elaborated in order to complement computational results.

With this, it has emerged the necessity to extend the evaluation metrics in order to deal with separation results of spatial scenes. We would like to suggest an evaluation system that infers position information by estimating ILD and ITD values for each separated source. This could be achieved by following the estimations discussed in Section 2.3.2. These retrieved cues need to be compared with some *universal* cues in order to obtain the source position in space. This kind of evaluation would allow

us to compare the position of the original source with that of the separated source. It would also allow to obtain spatial image stability metrics by monitoring position changes along time.

As we said before, there is a direct possibility of extending the proposed system to other kind of mixtures thanks to its adaptive nature. Possible applications would be: speech enhancing applications for bilateral cochlear implants, automatic music and non-music separation from VR videos or speech recognition enhancement for humanoid robots.

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